

Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics framework

Deliverable N. 1.9

30 September 2023

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¹ **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

² **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

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CC	Climate Change
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
D&I	Diversity and Inclusion
EC	European Commission
EIGE	European Institute of Gender Equality
ESF	European Science Foundation
EU	European Union
HE	Horizon Europe
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
GA	Grant Agreement
GE	Gender Equality
GES	Gender Equality Strategy of the European Commission
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSDs	Large Scale Demonstrators
RESIST	Regions for climate change resilience through Innovation, Science and Technology
R&I	Research and Innovation
SIA	Social Impact Assessment
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document was originally planned to provide the *analytical framework* to monitor the gender and ethics dimensions throughout the RESIST project. The original concept was built on the findings of the EC-funded PRO-RES project, whose results indicated the need for engagement to avoid the type of tokenism that can result from limited reach into the research community, and which risks reducing important work into boilerplate statements drafted by ethics and gender specialists tasked with them. For researchers, this provides little added value, and expert readers will easily recognise whether writers have gone beyond cut-and-paste to demonstrate compliance.³

The analytical framework was therefore created with this engagement in mind to assure the alignment of RESIST's scope, aims, and activities with the adopted ethical standards and with the principles of diversity and inclusion. However, while the framework has succeeded in the sense that the baseline information was provided and the funder-set ethics requirements met, the practicalities of large consortium with limited time quickly showed the difficulty of reaching the close engagement needed. There was also a clearly articulated need from the project and the EC alike that material should be provided in a resource-efficient way that would **not necessitate close engagement**. The document provides information on the causes and effects of these pain points, and the solutions taken.

In addition to describing the analytical framework, this document provides the state-of-the-art in the project at the time of writing and defines how, when and with whom the framework will be implemented. Efficient solutions to the classic project management triangle have been developed in response to the pain points and they will be improved and elaborated during the project. These solutions aim to simultaneously a) gather information from partners needed for the elaboration of ethics and gender issues b) provide the basis for developing tailored and fit-for-purpose operational guidelines beyond what is provided in this document c) set the indicators for monitoring compliancy and integration of ethics and gender dimensions within the project d) provide a quick method of flagging the need for guidance. This will permit the overall analytical framework to be implemented within the project in a cost-conscious way without compromising the goals of inclusion, gender equality and ethics.

The main action lines for implementation are within Ethics (Ethics framework), and Gender Equality (Gender framework), and these two frameworks are presented after the general approach and its timeline. The document includes several annexes to describe the Ethics and Gender issues,

³ https://prores-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/D4.6_Report-on-ProRes-interactions-FINAL.pdf

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compiling best practices known to be relevant at the time of writing towards achieving the goals of the framework, and including key background information for all RESIST partners to benefit from.

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1 Analytical framework concept

As stated in its name, the Inclusive Gender Equality and Ethics framework stands for:

- **Inclusion:** from consortium relations to research activities, the principle of inclusion is realized in the project's collaborative, co-creative, and participatory processes of partnership and cooperation, and respect for diversity. At no stage will discriminatory behaviour, harassment, bullying, or victimisation be allowed.
- **Gender Equality:** an action line cross-cutting all project activities in its dimension, with gender balance and gender mainstreaming pursued at every step of the project. This objective will be achieved through two lines of actions – general and specific. The general part includes gender consideration across the project's operations, whereas the specific part will focus on including gender considerations in the CCA research and innovation activities being pursued by the four demonstrators, their eight twinning regions and in the horizontal activities.
- **Ethics:** another action line, governing the standards of conduct for scientific researchers and the project's implementation, from ethically produced evidence to abiding by research integrity. This action line is built on continuous discursive engagement and recognition that codes, principles, checklists and recommendations cannot cover every situation. The action line facilitates interpretation, assessment, and application of research rules and guidelines in ethically sound ways.

The action lines of gender equality and ethics in the framework are pursued by the standard scientific logic of:

- 1) defining the nature, scale and scope of the analysis: where and why action is needed;
- 2) identifying drivers of change: with whom engagement is needed;
- 3) identifying anticipated outcomes: KPIs, checklists and other process mechanisms;
- 4) examining impacts and reassessing the actions, actors, and mechanisms as needed.

These action lines will be called 'Ethics framework' and 'Gender framework' respectively, to allow for more user-friendly references than the unwieldy but precise 'action line on [gender/ethics] dimension of the analytical framework'.

1.1 Overall timeline of the framework implementation

1.1.1 Initial setting

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The first step in any project is the Description of Action, which sets the starting point by describing the issues, actors, and the initial timing of actions. In RESIST, the framework is created under Task 1.4:

“This task will focus on implementing an analytical framework to monitor the ethics and gender dimensions throughout the project, assuring the alignment of RESIST’s scope, aims, and activities with the adopted ethical standards and with the principles of diversity and inclusion.

The task will: 1) implement and monitor compliance with adopted ethical standards and procedures, providing support and assistance to teams’ ethical challenges and updating the ethical guidelines in T5.3 as necessary; 2) set the framework and monitor the gender dimension and balance across the project by developing specific indicators and KPIs (data collection every 6 months); 3) co-create with WP/Task leaders a set of guidelines on the organisation of inclusive and gender equal activities, including collaborative demonstrator actions (WP3), stakeholder consultations (e.g. workshops, surveys in WP4), and other events to assure a shared knowledge on inclusive and gender equal practices; 4) review communication/dissemination activities and outputs with an inclusive gender lens to assure that diversity (of genders, ages, ethnicities, social backgrounds), inclusiveness and prevention of gender stereotypes are addressed.

At M60, a Ethics report will be developed with the periodic/final assessment results of Gender indicators and KPIs.”

For the Ethics framework, a connected task is Task 5.3: Data Management Plan & adherence to ethics requirements.

“The DMP covers ethics consideration to treatment and storage of personal/sensitive data. --- This task will provides operational guidelines/procedures to ensure that all work adheres to HE ethical principles and relevant EU, national and international legislation. The project activities raise ethics issues in Humans, Data, Artificial Intelligence and Environment, Health and Safety. An overview of those issues and applicable procedures to address them are documented in Part A. ESF will establish the Ethics Help Desk to guide and support the beneficiaries in addressing the data management and ethics issues according to best practices and applicable legislation. An external Ethics Advisor will be onboarded to get an additional expertise in Data/AI aspects, to be appointed at M2, will submit annual reports and get reimbursed for her/his contributions.”

In addition, ESF role as the Ethics Manager was set by the Consortium Agreement to align with these two tasks and ESF is a member of the consortium’s Executive Board.

1.1.2 RESIST M1-6

During M1-6 ESF began to

a) map the issues at hand to create the baseline,

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- b) gather the initial contacts to build the communication channels needed for actions,
- c) reassess the appropriateness of the actions planned and prepared the corrective amendments to both Description of Action and the project workflow, and
- d) provide the guidance and assistance required by partners.

At the project kick-off meeting the connections between the two tasks and actions for M1-6 were presented:

The slide is a blue rectangle containing four white boxes, each with an icon and text. The top-left box has a clipboard icon and is titled 'Concept: three key fields', listing 'Ethics', 'Gender equality', and 'Data management'. The top-right box has a rocket icon and is titled 'Role: guidance and support', listing 'Helpdesk (MS5.3, due in M2)', 'Review of outputs and activities', and 'Co-creation of key deliverables'. The bottom-left box has a network icon and is titled 'Role: Ethics and gender framework', listing 'information gathering' and 'assessing results and needs'. The bottom-right box has a speech bubble icon and is titled 'What to expect:', listing 'Requests from us to provide information we need to establish the framework' and 'Our availability to provide support for your activities and output creation'.

Figure 1. Kick-off Meeting presentation

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In the immediately following small group World café sessions a discussion on ethics and gender equality was initiated with the following triggering questions:

Triggering questions for

World café Ethics / Gender / Citizen engagement

Ethics

Baseline knowledge

- What do you think will be the ethics issues / pain points for you?
- Do you need help establishing the issues?

Help desk

Baseline operations: first steps to take with Ethics

- Do you need an ethics approval / opinion?
- Do you know where to get it? What would be the timeframe?

Practical issues

- We aim for continuous discursive engagement, but would a site visit be useful?
- What resources do you plan to use? We'd like to build a body of knowledge.

Gender, diversity

Interpreting the concept in the frame of RESIST

- Can you relate gender, diversity and inclusion to your work in RESIST?
- Can you think of the gender dimension of your activities in the project?

Operationalising the gender dimension in RESIST

- Would you value a single or a series of short webinars and / or guidance documents to help you to understand and personalise the expectations?
- We aim for continuous discursive engagement, but would a site visit be useful?

Figure 2. World Café triggering questions

In particular for Ethics, the need to gain any ethics approvals before the commencement of research activities requiring those approvals as set by law (see Annex: Ethics Issues) and acknowledged by all beneficiaries by signing of the Grant Agreement was discussed. This example is highlighted as representative of a pain point noted in earlier esp. H2020 projects: the assumption that beneficiaries are not responsible for their own transversal actions (like reporting, finances, ethics, gender equality, etc.). At the same time, experienced partners may interpret that monitoring means surveillance and policing, and that project frameworks are a hindrance rather than help. Both concerns must be addressed, and early action was therefore taken to pre-emptively address the risks that could materialise from misunderstandings. None of the frameworks can be implemented *for* the partners (whether they want that or not), frameworks can only be implemented *with* them.

In order to set the Gender Equality state-of-the-art of the consortium for the action planned within the Inclusive Gender Equality Framework, a baseline study was made. Of the 56 partners in RESIST project, 39 partners had a GEP at the time of proposal submission, additional six were developing and reviewing their GEP as of May 2023.

The RESIST consortium is composed of various types of organisations: 12 are Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), 9 are self-declared SMEs and non-profit organisations (including a company and one consultancy firm), 20 are government organisations (municipalities, ministries, other public bodies) and 14 are non-profit organisations or non-profit research organisations (excluding self-declared SME beneficiaries), and one is non-profit, public body, research organisation.

All 12 HEIs have GEPs, seven explicitly mention the advantages of gender perspectives in research and have established measures to promote it. The nine SMEs and non-profit organisations are not required to have GEP to qualify for HE funding, however, two have EDI policies, two have a GEP in place and one is developing a GEP. Of the 20 public bodies, all have GEPs or are developing/reviewing new GEPs in their organisation.

No consortium partner GEP addresses the content related GEP building block 'Integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation content' directly.

Some pain points identified for rectification from the first 6 months were:

- Non-mandatory obligations: ESF has obligations to review, assess, and monitor, but the partners provide the material on a voluntary basis. At the same time, and precisely because each partner has legal and institutional obligations towards ethics and gender equality, which they are duly performing, additional co-operation within the project can be perceived as optional.
 - o ACTION: framework to set the timeframe and actors for M7-60, and include further descriptions of the work, its purpose and added value. Within what resources permit,

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guidelines and instruction materials should be provided not only for the operational but at a more general level as well.

- Scale of the project: with 56 partners working on several concurrent actions, there will naturally be demand for attention and meetings, where non-mandatory obligations do not get priority. At the same time, necessary in-depth discussions in the field of ethics and gender equality are not ideal to conduct in large group settings.
 - o ACTION: interactions to accommodate for in-depth discussions on the specific topics of gender and ethics with partners at predictable intervals.

1.1.3 RESIST M7 – M60

From M7 onwards until the end of the project, the methodology will follow the initial logic and operate in 6 month cycles, duly corrected from the lessons learned from the initial approach:

- Each cycle will include an active data-gathering round for identification of outcomes related to ethics and gender equality, done separately from other data gathering for the project. *The first round was done together with other project partners to aim for synergies and avoid overloading the partners, but the complexity of the exercise made it clear that future rounds must take place with clarity of purpose and expectations, as well as independent of the workflows of unrelated tasks.*
- The data-gathering rounds will take place March-May and September-November each year e.g.: mid-cycle, except when project workflow would require adaptation. The ending points allow alignment with the Consortium Body meetings set to take place each December and June, with the adaptations and actions necessary taking place in the months preceding the next round of data-gathering. Continuous availability to any *ad hoc* interactions outside these periods is naturally assured.
- In addition to the bi-annual stock-taking, at M30 a public, intermediate report on KPIs' achievement and possible corrective actions will be delivered, and at M60 an internal report is foreseen.
- The initial list of actors will be regularly updated and expanded to accommodate for staff changes and per needs of the actions. While the effort required for this is substantial, the Ethics Manager will be supported by the Operational Project Manager responsible for keeping the address list of members and other contact persons updated and available.

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- While the production of internal guidelines beyond those provided in this document and the DMP is foreseen mainly for cycle M7-12, review and assessment work will take place over the course of the project to match with its needs and development, and guidelines will be updated and/or new ones will be produced upon need. This is with the caveat that general guidelines on ethics and gender can never fully replace the need for case-by-case assessment on what exactly is being done and planned, how will the plans be executed and what is the rationale and need. And without knowledge of the operational parameters and details, operational guidelines cannot be made.

Actions specific to the ethics and inclusive gender equality frameworks separately will be described as part of their more detailed descriptions in the following sections.

At the time of writing (M9) the continuous self-assessment had started and is producing expected results in terms of validation and monitoring of ethics and gender dimensions in the project. While the work is on-going, preliminary results suggest that the general starting point was correct: the need to exchange and create trust between horizontal and regional partners is of utmost importance and key to the full application of the framework. As ever, trust and shared understanding cannot be imposed, only facilitated with the help of appropriate tools and methods.

In a focussed effort to leverage synergies with sister project R4C, ESF has workshopped with its counterparts of R4C to discuss and mutually validate the Ethics and Gender frameworks / plans of both projects. This work was begun in M9 and has been productive. Future cooperation is planned to continue in, e.g., mutual exchange of state-of-the-art tools and materials for the two projects. Further exploration of potential exploitation pathways is not ruled out.

2 Ethics framework

2.1 Actors

Ethics HelpDesk was launched at the RESIST kickoff meeting by the contact details of ESF made available to the consortium. Further elaboration of the nature and scope of the activity was presented at WP1 and Executive Board meetings with the aim of ensuring that all consortium partners become fully aware of the HelpDesk's remit, role, and responsibilities. The Ethics HelpDesk has provided material and guidance to project partners starting from its very conception. See Annexes to the Ethics HelpDesk.

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While the Ethics HelpDesk has only had two contacts until end of M6, this should not be read as evidence of absence of ethical problems, since it may simply mean absence of evidence. ‘No contact’ does not translate into ‘no issues’. The presence of Ethics HelpDesk assures a low threshold of initial contact in confidence, but it cannot, and does not replace the need for continuous monitoring and regular data collection within the project. The Ethics HelpDesk experience in M1-6 has served to validate the key principles underlying the framework methodology: mutual exchange and engagement with the partners. Ethics HelpDesk will stay in place, but it is expected that most Ethics needs will be met via other means detailed below.

Ethics Commission was originally conceived as involving ESF, the external advisor, and Adelphi, the key partner involved with the technical assessment of procedures and methodologies to be used in the project. However, the engagement of an external Ethics Advisor on Data and AI being seen premature at M2, the first version saw the Ethics Advisor tasks arranged internally to the project as seen below.

Update 24/04/23
ESF

Ethics commission

- GA: "ESF runs an ethics commission that will be used as the main body responsible for assessing and validating the procedures and methodologies to be used in the project and in order to be compliant with the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon Europe."
- The Ethics Commission consists of ESF, KU Leuven and Adelphi
- This structure allows for three key requirements to be met:
 1. Avoiding conflicts of interest, as no single partner can run an Ethics body
 2. Queries presented to Ethics HelpDesk can be promptly escalated to the Ethics Commission when needed
 3. Avoiding duplication of work as the procedures and methodologies are in any case provided to the task leaders present in the commission

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Figure 3. Original conception of the Ethics Commission 24/04/2023

It is foreseen that the role marked for KU Leuven will be duly replaced by an external advisor at the earliest opportunity, and the establishment of the first version of the Ethics Commission was a proactive measure to prepare for all contingencies. So far, there has been no need for the Ethics Commission to meet, as the procedures and methodologies used are not at the level of complexity requiring escalation beyond what ESF as Ethics Manager can handle. This is partly due to the expertise, and partly because of the research design and workflow of the project where more complex actions take place later.

Consortium partners have provided specific contact points for issues involving data issues, and INOVA maintains a continuously updated list of key contacts for prompt action.

2.2 Methodology

Ethics framework requires **reiterative self-assessment, external ethics advice, monitoring structures, and possibility to ask for guidance**. The timing of these actions is as follows:

- Continuous self-assessment will be via the use of a spreadsheet available on the project SharePoint since M8. A living document, it will be expanded and refined as the project progresses and engagement deepens. As a practical tool it provides general checklists and waypoints following the same logic and document structure as HE Ethics self-assessment and will include Ethics aspects of the Data Management Plan to allow partners to use (or learn to use) known quantities. Additional benefits include:
 - o checklists work also as indicators for monitoring the integration of ethics standards and D&I principles in the project
 - o spreadsheet provides for possibility to flag problems and request aid and elucidations to match partner needs
 - the above two points facilitate the development of tailored advice and fit-for-purpose operational guidelines, reducing the risk of providing partners with the opposite
- Guided self-assessment happens during the bi-annual data gathering rounds, and will involve more in-depth consultations with horizontal partners and the key regional partners to ensure nothing falls between the cracks. These will correspond to the input gathered via the ongoing continuous monitoring and consortium, WP, and other meetings. The bi-annual cycle matches with project meetings.

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- External ethics advice is provided by the advisor. The advisor will submit 5 annual reports at the end of each year (2023-2027).

It should be noted that any reference to the spreadsheet in this document represents the state-of-the-art at M9. The tool, the guided self-assessment, and the input via the Ethics Helpdesk serve as the material for tailoring and updating all operational guidelines in the project.

3 Inclusive gender equality framework

3.1 Actors

To facilitate the implementation of the general part of the Inclusive Gender Equality framework, ESF will collate the initial list of gender equality representatives of the RESIST beneficiaries with the help of the persons identified as contacts for data gathering. For the development and implementation of the specific part of the 'gender dimension in the research innovation content' of the framework, the research lead of the relevant partners will be consulted for suggestion.

ESF has an active role assuring the mainstreaming of gender equality and diversity across the project; this is and will be further done by assessing the needs of the project activities and providing brief and concise guidelines and checklists. Moreover, RESIST partners are encouraged to contact ESF in case of additional and/or more tailored guidance is needed.

3.2 Methodology

The development of the **RESIST Gender Equality framework** is based on the three specific features characterising the commitment of Horizon Europe to gender equality in research and innovation, making it a cross-cutting priority:

- 1, Gender Equality Plan (GEP) which is an eligibility criterion for all public bodies, higher education institutions and research organisations from EU Member States and associated countries wishing to participate in Horizon Europe;
- 2, The dedication to increase gender balance with a target of 50% women in R&I overall with specific attention to boards, expert groups, evaluation committees, and research teams;
- 3, the integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation content of all R&I activities/projects.

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Correspondingly, RESIST Gender Equality framework builds upon the gender mainstreaming strategy (see ANNEX V: Definitions). Mainstreaming gender involves ensuring that gender perspectives and attention to the goal of gender equality (including gender balance) are central to all project activities, from project management to communication and research activities.

With this aim, the RESIST Gender Equality framework is composed of two parts:

- 1, **General Part** focusing on the implementation of non-research related, general features;
- and
- 2, **Specific Part** focussing on 'the integration of the gender dimension in the research and innovation' part of the projects.

The specificity of the RESIST Gender Equality framework is that it goes beyond gender equality and strives to apply an **intersectional approach** considering diversity factors such as age, disability, socio-economic backgrounds, religion, ethnicity, urban/rural that can be considered amplifying existing vulnerabilities to climate change related disasters. Using an intersectional framework to identify vulnerabilities to climate change impacts on local populations and using the findings can help design robust CC adaptation measures (see ANNEX VI: Relevance of considering gender and diversity dimensions in CC adaptation measures).

Adherence to the features formulated in the General Part will be required from all RESIST partners, while the development and implementation of the Specific part will be fine-tuned *with* and *for* the research and innovation partners for their scope of work in RESIST, in an iterative way over the 6M-cycles of the first half of the project - until M30.

3.2.1 General Part

As mentioned above, the implementation of this part of the framework is expected from all partners - as much as the requirements are relevant to their activities - in the form of the following actions:

- Collection of gender-disaggregated data that allows an intersectional analysis (e.g., sex, age, educational level – attributes, discussed and finalised together with relevant partners) at the overall project as well as local events, in expert teams, etc.
- Striving for the achievement of gender balance with a target of 50% women in R&I overall;
- Application of gender sensitive language in all communication, dissemination and outreach activities.

To this end

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- specific guidance documents will be prepared primarily in cycle M7-12; these guidance documents may need to be updated as the project progresses and if specific needs appear, new ones will be produced;
- as agreed with the communication partner REVOLVE, a common action plan will be developed to define the process for reviewing large volume or highly important communications of the project (M10);
- general Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be set during the period of M7-12; and corresponding data collection templates will be provided and then collected by ESF each March-May and September-November period, every year; and evaluated to be shared with the consortium at the Consortium Body meetings planned for December and June each year during the project lifespan.

The current planned guidance documents include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Inclusive communication guidelines and checklist for the communication partner REVOLVE (M11);
- Inclusive communication checklist for all RESIST partners (M11);
- Diversity in stakeholder engagement activities checklist (M12);

During the project lifetime other guidance documents, checklists and resources could be developed in response to specific project's needs. ESF is committed to capitalising from the knowledge and outputs generated by past and current EC-funded projects working on gender equality, making available to the RESIST partners the outputs that are relevant for them, and if needed, tailoring some of these to specific project activities.

3.2.2 Specific Part

In order to assure the integration of the gender dimension in the research and innovation context of the RESIST work, the framework will be shape-cut to specific settings, objectives and action lines of

- the demonstrators' activities – collectively to the 4 LSDs and twinning regions if applicable; and
- the horizontal partners / across project activities such as inclusive research and innovation activities, such as needs assessment, climate adaptation framework, policy analysis of climate change adaptation; inclusive social innovation strategies and social impact assessment.

Specific implementation steps per 6M cycle

- **Contextualisation** - aims the understanding of the specific relevant characteristics of the LSDs and twinning regions as per their RESIST work, and the scope of work of the horizontal

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partners, interpreting the collected information through an intersectional lens (cycle M7-12 only);

- **Discussion** - aims agreement on the scope of gender and inclusivity considerations in the work and the co-design, fine-tune and finalise of the KPIs to monitor integration of gender and diversity dimensions in the R&I context (cycle M7-12 only);
- **Data-gathering** for the specific KPIs hand-in-hand with the general data-gathering;
- **Technical support** based on need, e.g., mobilisation of relevant project partners for information exchange, sharing of best practices, and providing guidelines and checklists etc.;
- **Reflexivity** to assure the continuous work progress assessment, fine-tuning of existing KPIs, setting new ones, evaluating risks, what works and what needs to change to assure a progressive inclusive gender equality approach in R&I activities.

A guidance document (including a checklist) on “Diversity and gender dimension in research content” will be developed for the end of the cycle M13-M18, while already existing guidelines and recommendations from other projects and/or gender equality organisations (e.g. EIGE, UN women) will be shared with the RESIST consortium during the cycle M7-M12.

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Figure 4. RESIST Inclusive Gender Equality Framework

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ANNEXES to the Ethics Framework

This annex provides additional information on the legal basis for Ethics in RESIST, and on the Ethics issues identified in the project by M6.

ANNEX I: Legal basis

Legal basis for involving ethics in RESIST, a Horizon Europe project, is set by Regulation (EU) 2021/695 (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32021R0695>) and in particular, its article 19, "Ethics":

Actions carried out under the Programme shall comply with ethical principles and relevant Union, national and international law, including the Charter and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols.

Particular attention shall be paid to the principle of proportionality, to the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination and to the need to ensure protection of the environment and high levels of human health protection.

The operational requirements to each partner in the field of ethics and values are set under GA Art 14. The consequences of not meeting these requirements are not trivial, as listed in GA articles 28-32. A key operational document for consultation on the human rights aspect is:

<https://rm.coe.int/coe-humanrightsapproach-r01-v05-light-final-version/1680a22410>

A key legal requirement under this article is point 4:

Legal entities participating in an action shall obtain all approvals or other mandatory documents from the relevant national, local ethics committees or other bodies, such as data protection authorities, before the start of the relevant activities. Those documents shall be kept on file and provided to the Commission or the relevant funding body upon request.

To assist the speedy provision of the documents to the Commission by the coordinator as per the GA Specific Rules, RESIST provides on its SharePoint site a folder for depositing copies of the documents. If the documents are not in English, participants will submit the copies together with an English summary.

On a practical note, as Ethics bodies in Europe do not follow a commonly shared schedule, appointments times can vary. Partners are duly aware of this and have proceeded accordingly to

make the necessary arrangements as per their institutional requirements. The situation will be regularly reviewed and monitored during the course of the project.

The continuous monitoring spreadsheet provides a checklist for partners to indicate whether:

- National / local / other ethics committees approval/opinion/other is mandatory
 - o If yes, has it been obtained
 - If yes, has it been deposited in SharePoint with an English summary

SCOPE OF THE ISSUES

For the already known Ethics issues, the following presentation is built after the nomenclature of the Ethics Summary Report, where RESIST project involvement in Ethics issues is listed under five fields.

- Humans
- Personal data
- Non-EU countries
- Environment, health and safety
- Artificial intelligence

The reason for choosing this structure is not due to a particular attachment to the EC method of treatment but a conscious preference to allow consortium partners to refer to known quantities. The division by no means indicates that the listed items cover all and potential ethics issues, as is evident from the compliancy obligations from art 19. Accordingly, and as Ethics Summary Reports always duly state, **all ethics issues related to activities in the grant must be addressed**. To quote in full:

“This includes the ethics issues identified in the report and any additional ethics issues that may emerge in the course of the action. In case any substantial new ethics issues arise, beneficiaries should inform the granting authority. For each ethics issue applicable, beneficiaries must follow the guidance provided in the How to complete your ethics self-assessment document”.

In continuation, as stated on the 1st page of that document, titled ‘IMPORTANT NOTICE’ it is repeated that **not all ethics issues are covered by this classification**, nor is it meant to do so. The above list thus reflects the classic cases, as they are called in the manual, and there is due recognition that Ethics issues may and do arise in many areas. At the time of writing, no substantial new ethics issues not covered by this document have been reported nor found.

The Ethics framework thus needs to be comprehensive and allow for **reiterative self-assessment, external ethics advice, monitoring structures, possibility to ask for guidance**. This methodology provides a full and robust coverage of all ethical issues, whether they fall into pre-

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established lists or defy easy categorisation. Thus the division, while not representing the reality of often overlapping issues nor covering them completely, will nevertheless be followed since the categorization does set a baseline that makes the hard-to-understand into easy-to-use for learners and practitioners at every level.

The continuous monitoring spreadsheet will be expanded to accommodate new ethics issues that may arise in the course of the project, with case appropriate checklists/indicators.

Finally, with reference to the above-mentioned Important Notice, it is important to notice that the **first source of info will always be the beneficiary's own institution**. Nothing produced under the framework can supersede beneficiaries' own institutions guidance, rules, or approaches should they be stricter than the baseline set at project level.

Before engaging in the five (5) listed issues above, the key aspect of research integrity must be tackled, as respect of the fundamental principle of research integrity is among the legal requirements for Horizon Europe projects. However, as research ethics and research integrity are often separated on a conceptual level and academic discussion, the framework will specifically cover research integrity to ensure that conceptual discussions do not come in the way of legally binding commitments.

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ANNEX II: Integrity

The key document for research integrity is the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (<https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>). The GA enforces compliance with the following principles:

- reliability in ensuring the quality of research reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources
- honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair and unbiased way
- respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment
- accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts

By implication beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices including ensuring, where possible, openness, reproducibility and traceability and refrain from the research integrity violations described in the Code.

In addition to following the ALLEA Code, RESIST project integrates the principles in its in-consortium activities through the Code of Conduct set forth in the Project Handbook. For purposes of elucidation, the following examples are provided:

- Reliability: agreements made are honoured (for example, unjustified back-pedaling or escalation of demands afterwards is not allowed).
- Honesty: all partners refrain from dissimulation in their interactions or fait accompli approaches
- Respect: interactions happen with professionalism and collegiality, in a shared understanding, and towards mutual agreed goals.
- Accountability: responsibility for own actions, errors included.

The Project Handbook also bans any kind of discriminatory behaviour, harassment, bullying, or victimisation. In doing so, it connects and overlaps with the principle of inclusion and the goals of the Gender framework. It is explicitly recognised in RESIST activities how the aforementioned forms of violence involve **asymmetric relations of power**.

An imbalance in the power relations can be:

- real (as in a hierarchical work environment),
- perceived (hierarchy may be falsely assumed, e.g, from a title) or
- potential (expectations of future relations).

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These types of relations give room for violence based on **feelings of superiority**, and an intention to assert that superiority by humiliation with the goal to make a person - or a group of people - feel inferior and subordinate. This violence is often perpetuated by a culture of fear, denial and silence. In addition to the measures taken at each partner organisation, on the project level RESIST encourages partners to report any in-consortium violence in all its forms, whether it be abuse of power, sexist or racially charged language, bullying or gaslighting of colleagues, etc., to the Ethics Manager and the Project Coordinator.

The continuous monitoring spreadsheet includes a checklist to follow and to indicate whether:

- ALLEA code is clear / guidance in confirming interpretation is needed
- Project Handbook is clear / guidance in confirming interpretation is needed / suggestions for improvement are available

The importance of continuous monitoring is apparent in the need to ensure that all partners are aware of the changes in Ethics landscape that is fundamental for following the highest ethical standards. A case in point, the ALLEA code 2023 was revised in June 2023 to, inter alia, “accommodate heightened sensibilities in the research community to mechanisms of discrimination and exclusion and the responsibility of all actors to promote equity, diversity, and inclusion,” key aspects of the framework defined by this deliverable.

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ANNEX III: EC-flagged Ethics issues

Humans

Under Task 5.3 best practices are provided to partners via designated folder in the project SharePoint site. Documents provided so far are included as annexes to this document.

The continuous monitoring spreadsheet includes a checklist to follow and indicate whether:

- Common standards of outreach are clear / guidance is needed
- Checklist is clear and used
- For each of the three templates: is it used / adapted / own version is used
 - o If adapted, is the variant submitted to the relevant folder on SharePoint
 - o If own version is used, is it submitted to the same folder
 - Indication on the need to use own version (local requirement, etc.)

Further fit-for-purpose operational guidelines and procedures may be created on-demand and during the project with the implementation of this framework.

In terms of complexity of the methodology, the realized and planned research involving human participants in the project is done with standard social science assessment methods - user studies, surveys and interviews - and existing commercial technology is involved in user experience verification and validation. As the project progresses, any changes will naturally be monitored, engaged with, and necessary adjustments made according to the analytical framework.

Both in its internal data collection activities as well as its stakeholder relations, RESIST relies on participatory, co-creative, and inclusive processes of partnership and cooperation to ensure that the project provides ethically produced evidence with and for policy- and decision-makers on climate-change adaptation.

The continuous monitoring spreadsheet includes a checklist for indicating whether:

- Participants have been selected according to / acknowledging the project's DEI principles
 - o Which exclusion and inclusion criteria were applied
 - o Which stakeholder groups are represented

Dealing with **vulnerability** is a built-in element in RESIST, as the project aims to strengthen the resilience and accelerate the transformation and increase adaptive capacity of 12 climate vulnerable EU regions. For purposes of clarity and avoiding confusion when dealing with a suitcase term like vulnerability, the following precisions are needed:

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- Regions and persons alike are **vulnerable** to climate change. This is a statement of fact independent of ethics. Certain populations may be *more* vulnerable to, e.g., health impacts of climate change due to socio-economic factors (level of income, education, access to services, housing, etc.).
- **Vulnerable persons or groups** in the context of Ethics refer to persons *more* vulnerable than average for reasons such as lower-income, but also due to effects of discrimination, diminished mental faculties, and who thus require special protection. Examples include people with disabilities, migrants, refugees, LGBT persons, national minorities, and children.

RESIST builds as much as possible on the established practice in human rights jurisprudence, where vulnerabilities and discrimination are assessed on **context-sensitive grounds**. Categorising groups or people as permanently or inherently vulnerable risks *inter alia* perpetuating stereotypes, patriarchal behaviour, stigmatisation, and is thus legally and ethically suspect. However, RESIST recognises that some Research Ethics Committees may differ in their assessment of vulnerabilities from the project-level approach, and their decisions must be respected. The monitoring done under the frameworks will provide useful data on this topic for further research.

RESIST is dedicated to building both overall resilience while recognising the different adaptation needs due to context, person and group specific vulnerabilities. The outputs will be designed to take the needs of vulnerable persons and groups fully into account and thus ensure that no one is left behind. The generation of new research data needed for the development of those outputs by engaging volunteers from vulnerable groups is minimised by using historical or pre-existing data when available, in line with harm minimisation when redundant research activity would be risked. The partners already engaged in this data gathering have duly gained the required ethics approval for the data gathering and the procedures applied to ensure participants are not subject to any form of coercion and undue inducement. This applies also to how they handle the personal data.

The continuous monitoring spreadsheet includes a checklist for indicating whether:

- Vulnerability was identified and it is not possible to gain the data from other source:
 - o Is special attention paid to protecting their rights in terms of
 - Providing case-appropriate information and consent forms (especially when reduced ability to provide fully informed consent is at risk)
 - Abstaining from undue inducement (especially for economic vulnerability)
 - Whether the collection of personal data takes account of the vulnerabilities (especially if collection of special categories of personal data is involved and/or sensitive information content is collected)
 - The assessment basis of vulnerability (are they context-specific or based on categories of vulnerabilities)

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Personal data

From the perspective of legal obligations, and to repeat here the approach laid out in the RESIST Data Management Plan, gathering and processing of personal data will be done in full compliance with any European and national legislation relevant to the country where the data collections are taking place.

- **Each partner is responsible** for providing an adequate level of technical and organisational measures for secure storage, processing and transfer of all personal data, and will comply with GDPR requirements and other relevant legislation as required.
- In connection with research with human participants, each partner is responsible for securing participants' **informed consent** for the clearly stated purposes of the project and informing them or the contact person for updating or deleting their data. This applies also to any personal data gathered outside research activities needing appropriate consent.
- Partners also take responsibility for the **security of personal data** they possess in terms of both physical infrastructure and access policy, ensuring data protection by design and by default.
- In-consortium rules governing personal data exchanges between partner organisations are governed by Consortium Agreement article 4.4.

Partners will self-assess their research plans with the help of this tool <https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/ethics-data-protection-decision-tree/index.html> and the results will be indicated and monitored via the continuous monitoring spreadsheet. For ethical reasons, the spreadsheet will not ask any questions that would risk self-incrimination (for example, "are you fully GDPR-compliant?").

The key role of AugmentCity is highlighted, as their tasks include continual monitoring of the state-of-the-art cyber security measures and adherence to privacy preserving regulations reflecting on the latest EU/national policies and legislations and technical solutions in the market. This adds a further aspect of assurance to the flow of information to all consortium members in keeping up-to-date with data security in all its aspects.

Aligning with the needs of the Gender framework, RESIST acknowledges that data protection laws must be respected at all times, all data should be anonymised and stored in a safe way, but within those caveats, the **benefits of disaggregating data must be recognised**. Not only is it necessary for the purpose of implementing the Gender framework, but disaggregation is essential for e.g. addressing vulnerable groups as a matter of priority for CCA actions. Accordingly, it is elaborated here for the avoidance of doubt that while the project duly minimises the collection of special categories of personal data (formerly known as 'sensitive data') for the purposes of accounting for said vulnerabilities due to, e.g., ethnicity, *it is not illegal to collect data on these categories*, as long

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as it is not personalised, i.e., identifiable with an individual and securely stored. Section 5 of the DMP of the project provides the basic practical and operational guidelines for pseudonymisation and anonymisation of personal data.

Further to the legal obligations, and in accordance with the implementation of the Gender framework, operational guidelines related to personal data were originally conceived to be provided under Task 5.3 of the project to assist partners with designing and implementing their research in a way that goes beyond the legal minimum and into the realm of applied ethics, and the original conception above will be implemented by co-creation with the partners in case the logistical pain points at project level can be resolved. Otherwise, the engagement will be limited to the data gathering rounds. Questions foreseen to be addressed will include:

- When collecting personal data, how do individuals know what you are collecting, what for, and for how long?
- What interests are balanced when deciding what categories of personal data can and should be asked for?
- What are the ethical concerns on assessing whether individuals know what their controls are: for opting in/out, of what and how, and who to contact if they want to exercise their rights?
- What is the ethically sound level of transparency, how is clear and plain language assessed, etc.?

Figure 5. Common method to get explicit content : it's legal – but is it ethical ?

Non-EU countries

No research activities will take place in non-EU countries beyond the partners in RESIST consortium hailing from Norway and Ukraine. There will be NO exploitation of participants or local resources,

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nor activities that would be prohibited in the EU. From the viewpoint of ethical standards, the research planned outside the EU is like that planned inside the EU, thus ruling out the possibility of ethics dumping.

In terms of protection of personal data, Norwegian partners operate under GDPR. Ukrainian data privacy legislation in force, The Data Protection Law essentially complies with the EU Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC. Although it was superseded by GDPR in the EU, the level of data security legislation is sufficiently high. Moreover, the draft law “On Personal Data Protection” No. 8153 was submitted to Ukrainian Parliament last October. It has the goal of harmonizing Ukrainian data protection legislation with the standards enshrined by the GDPR and Convention 108+ of the Council of Europe, which is already fully effective in Ukraine (<https://www.dlapiperdataprotection.com/index.html?t=law&c=UA>). The above-stated approaches to personal data apply and the actions will be implemented also in the non-EC countries.

Ukraine is a lower-middle income country, but no discussion of research ethics considerations there can take place outside the current, tragic situation. It is by now well documented that the war of aggression waged by Russia on Ukraine poses deadly risks to anyone living in the internationally recognised territory of Ukraine. The indiscriminate destruction of civilian targets by forces under Russian command poses deadly risks to everyone in Ukraine, thus including the project teams and staff at University of Odessa. This is a sad fact, and the resulting conclusion that RESIST activities do not cause additional risks to the Ukrainian partners compared to their everyday life, while technically correct, can only be cold comfort to them. Nevertheless, it is similarly evident that refraining from RESIST activities would do nothing to increase the safety of their team either, and climate change adaptation will be needed in Ukraine independent of the war.

For obvious reasons, no project activities are planned for non-Ukrainian partners in Ukraine as long as the situation remains dangerous, as this would result in additional and perfectly avoidable risks. While on-site study or research exchanges are thus ruled out, collaboration and/or joint publication with local scientists will be explored as part of the benefit, data and results sharing due to an equal consortium partner, and based on reciprocity in open science. ESF in particular is able to explore opportunities to go beyond the GA-set minimum in responding to local needs by consider effective, longer-term capacity-building effort in the much-needed fields of science management and monitoring in Ukraine (see: <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-023-00505-3>).

Environment, health and safety

While the final scope of all the work in the field is yet to be established, but under the Ethics framework abiding by recognised procedures is facilitated in order to help keep teams and participants safe. The minimum standard established for each partner by the following best practices:

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- keep careful notes of all work engagements
- ensure projects are adequately staffed
- use mobile phones to keep in touch with the home base
- conduct full risk assessments of fieldwork sites
- formally notify authorities of activities being conducted in an area
- carry authorised identification
- prepare and train techniques for handling conflict, threats, abuse or compromising situations
- debrief after fieldwork with an assessment of safety and
- report on health and safety incidents.

As mentioned above, the situation in Ukraine poses evident and well-published threats to the local team's safety, compounded at the time of writing by the destruction of Kakhovka dam, but as stated, the project activities are not worsening the situation.

The continuous monitoring spreadsheet includes check for the above questions. In addition, it includes indicators for following relevant environmental legislation, and measures to avoid causing stress and anxiety which might result to stakeholders in the context of dealing with climate change.

In general, RESIST is built on a positive tone of optimism and empowerment to adapt to climate change, and thus aims to avoid all project communication, events, or research situations that could add to or cause stress or anxiety. Nevertheless, project partners acknowledge that the topics and the general theme may result in climate anxiety at personal, community, or even global level even when catastrophising is not the goal. RESIST adopts thus a posture of evidence-based research presented with a positive outlook of hope for the stakeholders. Naturally this applies also to the well-being of all project partners, colleagues and research participants in line with the approach defined above under Integrity.

While RESIST was not funded under strict requirement to consider the Do No Significant Harm principle of the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Finance, RESIST does involve climate change adaptation, and partners are recommended to consider the principle, as well as the criteria for sustainable economic activity in their activities and research plans. RESIST advocates considering the longer-term potential effects of their work for future generations (i.e., from the perspective of intergenerational ethics). The following list is provided for information purposes:

For a quickstart guide: <https://www.spglobal.com/esg/insights/a-short-guide-to-the-eu-s-taxonomy-regulation>

For a very long list of possible harms: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-03/200309-sustainable-finance-teg-final-report-taxonomy-annexes_en.pdf

For the law itself: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/852/oj#ntc60-L_2020198EN.01001301-E0060

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And recent legal developments: <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/EU-budget/parliament-seeks-amend-application-do-no-significant-harm-principle-eu-research>

On the last item, while there are plans to broaden the application of the DNSH principle to all projects under European R&I framework programmes, the legal situation is not yet set. Any change in legislation will naturally be complied with by the project.

Artificial intelligence

The sole specific GA-stated instance of using AI in the project is a subtask with a special focus to the human interface layer based on the Graphical Digital Twin (GDT). Rest of the technology used in the project represents minimal-risk AI. This includes applications such as AI-enabled video games, data analytics, spam filters, currently widely used in the EU and aligning with current legislation, jurisprudence and regulation. The goal of using this technology is beneficial, as it aims to empower the target groups to become active players in fighting the climate change, and one of the functionalities foreseen is accordingly inclusion of the citizen. Users will be made duly aware when interacting with AI technology is involved in order for them to take informed decisions whether to continue or step back.

For the GDT, the challenges are well recognised in: <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ai4ee/Documents/T-FG-AI4EE-2021-D.WG1.11-PDF-E.pdf>

“in citizen engagement in decision-making they are constricted to data-privacy and the fact that the sheer amount and heterogeneity of insights from various domains make it extremely demanding for non-experts to understand the situation and communicate priorities and solutions....

Finding a balance between high-quality data and data privacy, especially when the trust of the citizens in the local authorities is at stake.”

This is why in addition to the data privacy measures highlighted before, RESIST consortium involves local authorities as beneficiaries and leverages them for wide stakeholder engagement. It is also highlighted that the petabytes of earth surface data, data-processing with machine learning and AI is aimed at “making useful human comprehensible stories that engages a wide audience and helps in *triggering* decisions.” The “scenario-driven and insight-driven approaches are necessary to *nudge* stakeholders towards more sustainable high-level decisions”. The italics are added to emphasise that automated decision-making is not involved. The technology “helps in the decision-making process of short-term decisions but not on macro trends or multi-generational decisions”

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It should be noted that while the above or other foreseen use of AI does not raise significant ethics risks, or have potential to lead to significant negative individual, social and environmental impacts; stigmatisation or discrimination of people; interaction, replacement or influence on human decision-making processes, it was nevertheless seen fit for RESIST project to onboard an external Ethics Advisor to get an additional expertise in Data/AI aspects. The appointment of the advisor was initially foreseen at M2 of the project to precede the start of the task involved, but it soon came apparent that this was precipitated in view of the research design of the project. Ideally the technical framework development and deployment would be developed to a stage where an Ethics Advisor can be onboarded with full and meaningful specifications of the workload expected. The opportune time for this would be M14, after the framework deliverables D1.7 and milestones 9 and 12, and before the deployment of the Graphical Digital Twins. At the time of writing the Ethics Advisor is foreseen for M6.

Of course, the use of AI in any form is only one part of data ethics. In addition to the choice of tools and their use, RESIST partners will duly engage the connected issues of data ethics in overlapping fields, even in cases when they are handled within other frameworks, such as:

- Data governance, that is, who owns the data in-consortium (IP and knowledge management aspects).
- Transparency about the limitations of data and critical eye on AI results (part of research integrity).
- Biases will be considered and whether facts are being presented clearly: filters should be clearly identifiable and choices made wisely to avoid perpetuating bias (inclusion)
- Visualizations will be made appropriately accessible to the intended audience, who should be able to trace back the data in order to understand what is and is not shown. (communication and dissemination)

In general, data and its limits should be well understood, fit-for-purpose, and without giving any room for reproach over deception.

(Examples above adapted from <https://www.tableau.com/blog/headlines-headway-defining-data-ethics-and-its-impact-data-workers-93651>, for assumptions on the usefulness AI-generated results, see: <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-65735769>)

Finally, for publications RESIST partners are advised to consider the recent ICMJE guidelines for authors, especially its section 4: Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Assisted Technology when planning for dissemination:

“At submission, the journal should require authors to disclose whether they used artificial intelligence (AI)-assisted technologies (such as Large Language Models [LLMs], chatbots, or image creators) in the production of submitted work. Authors who use such technology should describe, in both the

cover letter and the submitted work, how they used it. Chatbots (such as ChatGPT) should not be listed as authors because they cannot be responsible for the accuracy, integrity, and originality of the work, and these responsibilities are required for authorship (see Section II.A.1). Therefore, humans are responsible for any submitted material that included the use of AI-assisted technologies. Authors should carefully review and edit the result because AI can generate authoritative-sounding output that can be incorrect, incomplete, or biased. Authors should not list AI and AI-assisted technologies as an author or co-author, nor cite AI as an author. Authors should be able to assert that there is no plagiarism in their paper, including in text and images produced by the AI. Humans must ensure there is appropriate attribution of all quoted material, including full citations.”

<https://www.icmje.org/recommendations/browse/roles-and-responsibilities/defining-the-role-of-authors-and-contributors.html>

The continuous monitoring spreadsheet covers at first the baseline documents:

- https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-by-design-and-ethics-of-use-approaches-for-artificial-intelligence_he_en.pdf
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>
- <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/pages/welcome-altai-portal>

As engagement deepens the checklist will expand to cover:

- If any risk assessment is needed, and whether the RESIST DMP needs to be accordingly updated?
- Have potential Ethics risks have been discussed with the Ethics Commission?
- Is documentation available about any ethics risks and their mitigation measures?
- Have potential negative impact (social, environmental, etc.) been assessed?

It should be noted that RESIST project focusses on the tools used in the research activities. Expansion can be made if the need arises, but the presence of AI alone is not sufficient cause: project sees no need to assess individual partners' choice of spam filters, translation software, etc.

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ANNEXES to the Inclusive Gender Equality Framework

ANNEX IV: Boundary conditions

- Council of Europe Gender Mainstreaming Toolkit
<https://rm.coe.int/final-gender-mainstreaming-toolkit-february-2019/168092e8f9>
- EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020 – 2025
https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en
- EU LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020 – 2025
https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/combating-discrimination/lesbian-gay-bi-trans-and-intersex-equality/lgbtiq-equality-strategy-2020-2025_en
- Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in R&I,
<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-12044-2021-INIT/en/pdf>

ANNEX V: Definitions

Diversity

Diversity, put simply, is the qualities and characteristics that uniquely differentiates every individual. However, in RESIST, diversity does not mean “we are all different”. In the project, diversity is defined as distinct categories or groups of people (not considered mainstream part of the society), with perceived and recognised similarities in a particular national context, and belonging to these groups, could impact how they experience CC and/or CCA measures or get impacted by them.⁴ For example, adaptation measures like dikes as flood protection can impact access to the sea and thus livelihoods of people who are dependent on the sea. Diversity in research can be understood as considering and including people of different racial and ethnic groups, age, and other identities who are otherwise underrepresented in research projects and practices.

Gender mainstreaming

The European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) defines gender mainstreaming as involving “the integration of a gender perspective into the preparation, design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of policies, regulatory measures and spending programmes, with a view to promoting equality between women and men, and combating discrimination.”⁵ Gender mainstreaming in RESIST means integrating a gender perspective in addition to promoting equal gender representation at all project activities, from the management of the project to the research and communication activities.

Inclusion

Inclusion refers to perceptions of people that they are able to contribute fully and effectively in society, in research, in organisations, etc. and that their participation is encouraged.

Intersectionality

⁴ Adapted from Mor Barak’s definition of diversity which is broadly in the context of organisations and relates to employment outcomes to make it more applicable to the RESIST project’s goals.

⁵ “What is gender mainstreaming”: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/what-is-gender-mainstreaming#toc-gender-mainstreaming-cycle>

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EIGE defines intersectionality as an “analytical tool for studying, understanding and responding to the ways in which sex and gender intersect with other personal characteristics/identities, and how these intersections contribute to unique experiences of discrimination”.⁶

Vulnerability (to climate change)

The extent to which a natural or social system is susceptible to sustaining damage from climate change and is a function of the magnitude of climate change, the sensitivity of the system to changes in climate and the ability to adapt the system to changes in climate.⁷ Vulnerability varies widely across communities and regions and sectors and depends on exposure and adaptive capacity.

⁶ Available at: <https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/thesaurus/terms/1050>. Accessed June 5, 2023

⁷ The term vulnerability can be framed differently accordingly to the field of research and has no single definition. The definition used here is in the context of climate change and is provided in Olmos, S., (2001) Vulnerability and Adaptation to Climate Change: Concepts, Issues, Assessment Methods. Climate Change Knowledge Network (CCKN).

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ANNEX VI: Relevance of considering gender and diversity dimensions in CC adaptation measures

Recent extreme weather events like storms and hurricanes, droughts, forest fires, and heat waves, floods, and sea level rise⁸, have been attributed to anthropogenic climate change. Generally, men and women are considered to be equally affected by a disaster, and that in life and death situation, gender equality is meaningless. However, nothing is farther from reality. Moreover, the idea that technocratic solutions treat everyone equally is also flawed (e.g., car safety tests done with dummies based on male bodies, sensors failing to recognise people with darker skins). There are gender differences (more nuanced differences arise when variables such as race and socio-economic background are added to this binary concept of men and women) in the way people perceive, experience, and adapt to hazards and risks. There are many studies which provide evidence that climate change has gender-differentiated effects (in other words, women and men, and of different ages, race, socio-economic backgrounds, may get differentially impacted by CC emergencies).⁹ One can perhaps argue that men's decisions (e.g., CEOs and governance boards of Shell and Exxon had knowledge about the possibility of CC with increased fossil fuel burning) are one of the key causes of anthropogenic climate change¹⁰ as traditionally women have been underrepresented in decision-making as well as in science and research. The status quo continues to be maintained as technology and technological fixes are seen as panacea for CC mitigation and adaptation, thus again focussing on the traditionally masculine professions of Engineering and Technology (In Finland, for example, females starting engineering is 18%, whereas in Denmark it is 30% leading to gendered outcomes by field of study and employment.¹¹)

⁸ Available at: <https://www.climate.gov/news-features/understanding-climate/climate-change-global-sea-level>. Accessed May 1, 2023.

⁹ Sightsavers (2015) Disability, disasters and empowerment: Evidence from qualitative research in a disability-inclusive disaster preparedness programme. London: Sightsavers; Erman, Alvina; De Vries Robbe, Sophie Anne; Thies, Stephan Fabian; Kabir, Kayenat; Maruo, Mirai. 2021. Gender Dimensions of Disaster Risk and Resilience: Existing Evidence. World Bank, Washington, DC. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/35202> License: CC BY 3.0 IGO; Eriksen, S.H., Brown, K. and Kelly, P.M., 2005. The dynamics of vulnerability: locating coping strategies in Kenya and Tanzania. *Geographical Journal*, 171(4), pp.287-305.

¹⁰ Daggett, C. (2018). Petro-masculinity: Fossil Fuels and Authoritarian Desire. *Millennium*, 47(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305829818775817>; <https://theconversation.com/what-big-oil-knew-about-climate-change-in-its-own-words-170642>. Accessed May 1, 2023.

¹¹ Vuorinen-Lampila, P., 2016. Gender segregation in the employment of higher education graduates. *Journal of Education and Work*, 29(3), pp.284-308; Naukkarinen, J.K., Bairoh, S., 2020. STEM: A help or a hinderance in attracting more girls to engineering? *Journal of Engineering Education* 109, 177–193. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jee.20320>

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It has been reported that climate related disasters are gendered as men and women experience disasters differently. Any disaster can bring forth long-term physical, mental, and emotional traumatic injuries and these traumas often show gendered patterns. For example, a study done to analyse gender differences in prevalence of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), with data from 13507 participants from Denmark and Iceland, reported that women had a two-fold higher prevalence of PTSD than men and it was found that females were more vulnerable to PTSD after disasters and accidents, followed by loss and non-malignant diseases.¹² Disasters magnify people's vulnerabilities which are influenced by gender. For example, evacuation responses to Hurricane Katrina were found to be gendered, where more men than women chose to stay to face the storm, irrespective of parenthood status, and women, particularly with dependent children, evacuated before the hurricane made its landfall. Similarly, low income, young people decided to not evacuate due to the fear of losing their jobs. People who experience the greatest negative impacts after a climate disaster generally are groups who were disadvantaged prior to the destructive event and gender is pivotal as regards the distribution of exposure in this aspect.

Similarly, perception of climate change-related risks and environmental degradation is gendered, i.e., studies have found differences in men's and women's levels of concern about environmental risk¹³, where women express higher levels of concern than men. Furthermore, women tend to adopt more green approaches to housework (which sometimes, can indirectly increase their daily burden of work), and focus more on social and ecological approaches than technological fixes (though it is accepted that technological fixes are necessary to mitigate and adapt to climate change). Energy consumption as well as attitudes and behaviors towards energy consumption are also gendered. For example, it has been reported that women consume more energy compared to men,¹⁴ whereas men (STEM educated, high income) take part in renewable energy cooperatives and investing in wind-

¹² Ditlevsen, Daniel N., and Ask Elklit. "Gender, Trauma Type, and PTSD Prevalence: A Re-Analysis of 18 Nordic Convenience Samples." *Annals of General Psychiatry* 11, no. 1 (October 29, 2012): 26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1744-859X-11-26>.

¹³ Slovic, P., 1999. Trust, emotion, sex, politics, and science: Surveying the risk-assessment battlefield. *Risk analysis*, 19, pp.689-701; Finucane, M.L., Slovic, P., Mertz, C.K., Flynn, J. and Satterfield, T., 2013. Gender, Race and Perceived Risk: The 'White-Male' Effect. In *The Feeling of Risk* (pp. 125-139). Routledge.

¹⁴ Lee, Seunghui, Sungwon Jung, and Jaewook Lee. "Prediction Model Based on an Artificial Neural Network for User-Based Building Energy Consumption in South Korea." *Energies* 12, no. 4 (January 2019): 608. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12040608>; Rätty, R., and A. Carlsson-Kanyama. "Energy Consumption by Gender in Some European Countries." *Energy Policy* 38, no. 1 (January 1, 2010): 646–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.08.010>

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farms and PV installations for solar energy,¹⁵ though in surveys, women have preferred renewable energy options.¹⁶

There has been gendering of climate change policy responses, which have mainly focused on scientific and technological measures (men's domain of activities) to tackle climate change problems without any consideration for how vulnerable men and women, girls, and boys, and their political and economic environments influence their ability to access public services and respond to climate change. Thus, reviewing existing policy documents (or developing new ones), adaptation plans and laws and climate change adaptation plans for differential effects using a gender and intersectional lens is important for social justice and to avoid controversies and unintended consequences or potential maladaptation. In the Aqua Domitia program supported by the Occitanie / Pyrénées-Méditerranée Region in France, the main concerns raised were about inequitable access to water resources at the territory level, rural/urban divide and costly technological lock-ins (which does not promote reduced consumption of water). Similarly, use of bioenergy crops could cause negative externalities associated with invasive species or reduce biodiversity in the area.

Women continue to perform and take responsibility for most of the reproductive work and caring work. Women also do most of the community management work as well as in building and maintaining social and familial networks. Such work is unpaid, often invisible and overlooked. The discourses of sustainable lifestyles and ethical consumption, though an ethical and responsible approach, generally reflect a feminine set of concerns and largely have been taken up by women (though counter positions exist, e.g., women employed in forestry industries resisted changes to conventional forestry practices¹⁷). Thus, it is important that gender and other diversity attributes are considered in how climate change and its policies are framed, and how the challenges are tackled as vulnerabilities and power imbalances can impede/dampen adaptation success to climate change. It is important that protection and assistance provided in emergency situations (e.g., women could need more lead time to evacuate depending on factors, such as caring responsibilities, and hence early warning systems can be designed considering these multi-layered aspects;¹⁸ is planned and implemented in a way that benefits women and men equally. In RESIST, the binary gender

¹⁵ Standal, K., Talevi, M., Westskog, H., 2020. Engaging men and women in energy production in Norway and the United Kingdom: The significance of social practices and gender relations. *Energy Research & Social Science* 60, 101338. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101338>

¹⁶ Clancy, J. and Roehr, U., 2003. Gender and energy: is there a Northern perspective? *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 7(3), pp.44-49.

¹⁷ "Taking Stands: A Feminist Perspective on 'other' Women's Activism in Forestry Communities of Northern Vancouver Island." Accessed May 1, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1080/713668882>.

¹⁸ Available at: <https://public.wmo.int/en/resources/bulletin/gender-equality-context-of-multi-hazard-early-warning-systems-and-disaster-risk>

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perspective, despite its limitations is valued, as gender considerations in adaptation measures and related decision-making in the global north is severely limited, not to mention limited inclusion of perspectives from marginalised groups.

Having better knowledge about communities residing in areas that would be prone to negative effects from climate change, is a robust defence against harm to these communities. RESIST's adaptation trials aim to be situated in communities to be able to include marginalised perspectives and has the goal to explore and design CCA measures including gender (intersectional) perspectives.

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ANNEX VII: Simplified preliminary framework with possible KPIs

Dimension	Characteristic element / project activity (non-exhaustive)	Aspects to be considered for operationalisation of the framework	Possible Indicators
General Part			
Institutional level	GE policies and plans	Information gathering on GE policies or plans (every 6 months)	No. of partners having GE policy and/or plan before project initiation; no. of partners in the project with GE Policy, GE Plan, EDI policy in place (or initiated) by the end of the project. GE policies or plans with gender in research explicitly mentioned
Gender specific data collection and analysis	Project level events, such as meetings and workshops	Who leads the meetings, who are participating in the meetings, are women/men encouraged to attend the meetings; identifying issues in achieving gender balance.	No. of women/men in meetings and in various committees of the project, women/men leading the work packages and chairing meetings.
Gender sensitive language adhered to in project communications	Digital Communication, and outreach	Use of gender-neutral language in texts. In visuals and images and virtual interactive exhibits, taking care not to reproduce gender stereotypes. Customised communication materials for various groups of people.	Communication materials created with considerations for diversity and inclusion
	Dissemination and organising project events (e.g., final conference)	Inviting women/men speakers.	Percentage of women/men in panels or no. of women/men as speakers
Specific Part			
Horizontal partner level	Social impact assessment	Inclusion of gender in social impact assessment (SIA) analysis	Gendered SIA
	Social innovation strategies	Understanding who benefits from the innovations and why.	Gendered Social innovation strategies
	Climate Change adaptation framework and plans, policy analysis of climate change	Gender considerations in reviewing and creation of CCA framework, gender considerations in CC policy	Vulnerability clearly articulated in documents to facilitate ways to address the consequences of CC

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Dimension	Characteristic element / project activity (non-exhaustive)	Aspects to be considered for operationalisation of the framework	Possible Indicators
	adaptation; analysis of public funding opportunities supporting CCA innovations	analysis, CCA programmes and plans and regulations; special condition for women/men and minority groups to access public funds for CC innovations	and associated adaptation measures from an intersectional perspective. Cluster analysis available to identify socially vulnerable people.
Gender specific data collection and analysis	Surveys, workshops, meetings, interviews	Understand how men, women and other social identity categories differently relate to the problem/issue Collecting data disaggregated by sex; use of an intersectional approach to data collection when possible.	Participation of diverse people representative of the population characteristics of the region, with focus on vulnerable people (CC risks) Gendered analysis of data and information gathered No. of women/men who participated in the events. No. of women/men facilitating the events
Inclusiveness in the demonstration activities	Surveys, co-creation workshops, dialogue with citizens, and citizen science activities	Understanding the demographic profile and socio-economic-cultural aspects of the people at the sites and involving diverse people in various project activities. Designing surveys and questionnaires to include gender aspects Collecting data disaggregated by sex; use of an intersectional approach to data collection when possible.	People from different social identity categories ¹⁹ involved Survey questionnaires designed to capture gender dimensions of the respondent Gendered analysis of data and information gathered
	Demonstration of CCA solutions	Identification of the stakeholders and their social identity categories (e.g., sex,	Diverse stakeholders engaged in meetings and co-creation workshops;

¹⁹ Social categories such as sex, race, class, physical and mental disability, education, location, immigration status intersect to create individual identities.

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Dimension	Characteristic element / project activity (non-exhaustive)	Aspects to be considered for operationalisation of the framework	Possible Indicators
		<p>age, socio-economic background) to assess who is willing to invest in CCA solutions, and why; Including people from various social categories and identities in the design of the solutions; Understanding the intersecting power relationships between various types of stakeholders; Consideration of marginalised people in CCA solutions; how they will be used by various people and how different people will be benefitted by these systems</p>	<p>motivations of diverse stakeholders assessed for investing in CCA solutions; No. of people from different social identity categories involved in the demonstration activities. Number of stakeholder representatives that are women/men and vulnerable groups; inclusive design</p>

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ANNEXES to the Ethics HelpDesk

ANNEX VIII: Ethics HelpDesk

Ethics HelpDesk

RESIST, like any Horizon Europe project, sets requirements to each partner in the field of ethics and values under GA Art 14. The consequences of not meeting these requirements are not trivial (cf. GA articles 28-32). To help all partners meet these requirements, RESIST foresees a comprehensive Ethics framework. A key aspect of this framework is the Ethics HelpDesk.

What does the Ethics HelpDesk do?

The Ethics HelpDesk is there to provide answers to all consortium partners' Ethics questions. Its role is to provide guidance and support for those in need. It also provides an easy access point for any partner who would like help to develop their procedures or methodologies. The Ethics HelpDesk is not established to investigate anyone, but aims to provide guidance and support including also advice on hypothetical scenarios.

How to contact the Ethics HelpDesk:

The first line of contact is to email [redacted] and [redacted]. The initial response to the inquiries will be provided within 10 days, however the time needed for a solution will depend on the difficulty level of the issue. This will be discussed with you as per our practice of continuous discursive engagement. This is an approach where ethical issues are tackled and settled before they become urgent problems or emergencies. This open-door policy is what separates a helpdesk from a hotline.

Scope of Helpdesk activities:

In line with the aim of keeping a low threshold for contacting the Helpdesk, questions do not have to be limited to research ethics alone. We will guide you to the relevant instance as necessary, and all questions are valuable input to developing a common body of knowledge in RESIST. At the same time, the Ethics HelpDesk is provided by ESF, which is not an external partner but a member of the consortium and thus bound by RESIST GA and CA. Confidentiality will be respected within the limits set by those documents.

Examples of situations where the HelpDesk can guide and support (a non-exhaustive list):

Research involving human participants

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- This means surveys, interviews or anything where you need to get the participants' consent. We can help you ensure that your consent forms and information provided about your research and personal data gathering is up to HE standards.
- We can do the same for your procedures to find and choose the research participants, and that the criteria for including and excluding them is ethically sound.
- Also, we help you if the participants represent vulnerable individuals or groups, or in any other situation where you need help to interpret the project documentation, whether it concerns research participants or the safety of your research staff.

Personal Data

- Advice on how to deal in an ethically sound way with the personal data needed for your research can be provided, e.g., recommendations on how to check that the personal data gathered is relevant, limited to the purposes of the research project, and collected in appropriate manner should it be sensitive personal data.
- We can also help you with any questions related to research data management, e.g., advice on how data must be collected, generated, processed, and/or made available.
- You can also forward to us any requests from research participants who may ask who to contact for controlling their personal data.

Non-EU countries

- Ethics HelpDesk activities are by no means restricted to EU, and we welcome questions related to research ethics when carried out outside the EU.

Artificial Intelligence

- RESIST work plan foresees an expert to assist in AI ethics, but you are welcome to approach the Ethics HelpDesk for any AI related issue, whether it concerns participants, research design, etc.

Environment, Health and Safety

- Climate change research naturally involves environmental, health and safety issues, and Ethics HelpDesk is an easy route to find guidance on how to keep your research up to the HE standards.

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ANNEX IX: documents provided via Ethics HelpDesk (from May 11, 2023)

Common standards of outreach / operational guidelines for general and specific settings

Ethically conducted research activities will be key in ensuring the quality and relevance of RESIST research results and recommendations. Common standards of outreach to human participants in the research is a fundamental part of the project's Ethics framework.

These standards are divided into 3 parts as per their setting.

General setting

- Participation will always be entirely voluntary
- Potential and actual participants will get clear and intelligible information, in relevant languages:
 - on the purpose of the research
 - the voluntary nature of their participation
 - their rights as research participants including how their data will be used and stored
 - the format of the research event
 - the identity of the project consortium and the identity of the researcher involved.
- Legal setting: respect of the articles 3, 8 and 13 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights relative to the
 - 'right to the integrity of the person',
 - 'protection of personal data', and
 - 'freedom of the arts and sciences'.

The principles of responsibility that apply in general toward participants:

- Respect of the integrity and dignity of persons
- Confidentiality of their personal information
- Proportionality:
 - Do not impose more than necessary on the participants
 - Do not go beyond stated objectives -
- Protection from harm and discomfort

Specific setting 1: dealing with vulnerable groups and individuals

The results of the research will benefit the groups represented by the participants, and to ensure that the research itself is also conducted ethically:

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- Key personnel must have expertise in studies involving vulnerable groups.
- Participants will be interviewed, on voluntary basis and following all the measures applying in the general setting.
- The information sheets must make clear that participation in the study will not have implications for the participants that would put them in harm's way or at risk.
- When considering the concerns research raises, build an understanding that all benefits of this research are for the good of society.
- The burden involved must be minimal.

Established key principles and procedures to protect interviewed vulnerable individuals that will be followed:

- Acknowledge the power dynamic in the interview situation where the interviewer as the relatively privileged party might be probing on highly personal topics
- The interviewer must seek to hand some of that power back, for example:
 - Apply techniques for data collection that are designed to let the interviewee be in control of where to take the interview, what to share, and how to tell their story.
 - Ask only an initiating, open, question, and make clear that the interviewee will not be expected to share anything they do not themselves volunteer to share.
 - The interviewee decides on the time and place of the interview.
 - The interviewee does not have to answer any questions or talk about anything they do not want to.
 - The interviewee can end the interview at any moment if they feel so inclined.
 - Informed consent is sought.
 - The interviewee can choose the level of recording they are ok with (full video, audio-only, notetaking only).
 - Privacy will be respected, and the interviewees will be informed about exactly how and at what level their identity and anonymity will be protected.

Specific setting 2: dealing with victims/survivors of gender-based violence or people at risk of gender-based violence

International guidelines and recommendations must be followed (e.g., the WHO & PATH measures on Researching Violence Against Women: A Practical Guide for Researchers and Activist, and the World Health Organization published guidelines for addressing ethical and safety issues in gender-based violence research.)

Specific measures to protect and minimise the risk of stigmatisation:

- Recruitment will only take place via researchers' already established networks (for instance, women's NGOs) and upon recommendation. No victim/survivor of gender-based violence will be contacted directly without prior consent and introduction via her network.
- Victims/survivors will only be contacted at a time previously agreed, as to minimise the risk of a partner finding out she is participating in the study, as the act of speaking to

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another person without a controlling or abuse partner's knowledge may trigger further abuse.

- Only one woman per household/family will be interviewed, in order to avoid alerting other women who may communicate the nature of the study back to potential abusers.
- No victim/survivor assessed as in a currently unstable situation will be interviewed.
- National Researchers are trained to refer women requesting assistance to available sources of support.
- Information about women's shelters/refuge and helplines will be provided.
- The interviews will take place in complete privacy, with the exception of children under the age of two, and at a date and time of the victim's/survivor's choosing.

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Checklist

This checklist is to help you ensure that your research is ethically sound in a user-friendly way. We advice all researchers to consult RESIST Ethics framework common standards of outreach.docx first. Ethics HelpDesk can be contacted for further information if needed. Note that while the structure follows the EC guidelines, some items do not have an option due to Grant Agreement commitments.

Considerations before the research is launched:

- Are the participants volunteers?

The only answer is yes as per GA. Involve only adults that can give fully informed consent.

- Check that their recruitment, inclusion and exclusion criteria (I.e., how were they chosen?) are ethical. If you are not sure, contact Ethics HelpDesk to verify.
- Check that you have informed consent procedures in place with participant statements, consent statement, informed consent and information sheets, providing details on unexpected findings policy. There are templates available in Ethics HelpDesk folder to this effect.
- Check that you have gained any ethics approvals if those are required.

Are the participants potentially vulnerable individuals or groups?

- If yes, what type of vulnerability is in question? This may affect the recruitment, inclusion and exclusion criteria and informed consent procedures above. See the Common standards for details.
- Check that you have procedures to ensure participants are not subject to any form of coercion and undue inducement (for example, you are offering payment that would cause participants to participate when they otherwise would not).

In case you are gathering any personal data:

Check that the participants receive the necessary information about

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- Informed consent and participants rights (The templates available have basic information at the project level but needs to be checked against your organisation's privacy policy)
- Contact details of your Data Protection Officer or other relevant responsible
- Information if the data will be transferred outside GDPR jurisdiction

Does your research involve the processing of special categories of personal data (e.g. sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, genetic, biometric and health data, political opinion, religious or philosophical beliefs)?

The only answer is no as per GA.

From the RESIST gender framework perspective we recommend gathering data about gender in all research activities when possible.

Participant information and consent form

RESIST

Regions for climate change resilience through Innovation, Science and Technology
(GA n. 101093968)

1. Introduction

My name is [interviewers, fill this part with your personal information, for example: Nemo Impune, I am job title at workplace, country]. I'm contacting you to invite you to participate in [for example, "an interview"] for a study within RESIST, a project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme [add more if applicable].

I'm contacting you to ask if you would like to participate in an interview about [use the same word / sentence here as in part 4. Procedure]. Your name was provided by [add contact – this is optional information]

2. Purpose of the research

The aim of RESIST is to [adapt as applicable for your research and location, the below is simply an indicative example from project abstract] strengthen the resilience and accelerate the transformation and increase adaptive capacity of 12 climate vulnerable EU regions, implementing 4 large-scale demonstrators of resilient innovations for Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) with quintuple-helix partnerships (including 1 in a less developed region) and promote transfer of know-how and innovative solutions to 8 twin regions (of which 4 less developed regions) through both physical mutual-learning activities and innovative immersive digital twins.

You and your experiences are important to our qualitative research. The RESIST researchers are [adapt here as applicable, "conducting interviews", "running a survey", "collecting data", etc].

3. Participation in the project and right to withdraw

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If you consent to participate, it means *[the following is for an example adapt as necessary, participating in one interview that will last approximately one hour. The interview can be conducted online or offline, at a public place of your choice, and will be conducted in [enter language here]. The interview will be audio recorded, transcribed and pseudonymised. This means that we will switch identifying information in the data with a pseudonym. This keeps your identity confidential, but allows us to re-identify you later if necessary. The audio recording will be destroyed [adapt timeframe to local context if necessary] two years after the end of the project, at the latest. [enter either “I am the only person who” or “the country research team members are the only people who”] will have access to the audio recording and transcript. The only data shared with the larger RESIST consortium is [adapt here as applicable].]*

Your participation in the interview is entirely voluntary. It is your choice to participate or not. Before you start telling your story, the information in this document must be provided to you. You will be asked to either read or carefully listen to me as I read it, and sign it to consent, either by in print, electronically, or via voice recording.

You may withdraw your consent and opt out of the interview at any time, and you may do so without any explanation and with no consequences for your relation to me, *[enter your organisation]*, or the RESIST partners *[define who]*.

You do not have to answer any questions you do not wish to. You have the right to retract the data you have provided (or remove portions of them), including your personal data: however, removing any data already used with your permission in publications, reports or open datasets is not possible. If you wish to exercise your right to withdraw after this interview, you will need to contact the Principal Investigator, with no need to explain why you want to withdraw (contact data below).

4. Procedure

We expect you to tell your story in a free, clear and honest form, describing your personal experiences of *[use the same word / sentence here as in part 1. Introduction]*. There will be very few questions, the story – the narrative – is yours to tell, but you are still free to skip a question or stop your story, the interviewer/listener will move on. No one else but the interviewer/listener will be present, unless you yourself would like someone else to be there. Once the interview is finished, the recording will be transcribed, and pseudonymised as described above.

5. Data protection

All project RESIST activities comply with *[enter General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and any relevant national legislation]*. All personal data collected will be kept secure and no personal data will be kept for longer than necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. Personal data

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which is no longer required for the purposes of the RESIST project will be deleted, and [*adapt timeframe to local context if necessary*] all recordings will be deleted at the end of the project, at the very latest.

Most importantly, we use your personal data only with your permission. To exercise your rights to access, rectify, erase and restrict your personal data, you can contact:

[*insert name and contact details of your DPO here.*]

[*add mention of any data processing if applicable*]

You also have the right to file a complaint with your local Data Protection Agency.

6. Anonymity and confidentiality

The personally identifiable information gathered via the interview will be kept in the strictest confidentiality and will be safely stored and destroyed [*adapt timeframe to local context if necessary*] two years after the end of the project, at the latest. Only [*enter "me" or "the research team at ____"*] will have access to non-pseudonymised data. Your personal data will be kept confidential and will only be disclosed to the wider team of the RESIST project on a need-to-know basis, after requesting your explicit consent. It will not be disclosed to any other individual or third parties.

7. Possible risks, disadvantages or discomfort, incidental findings

Your participation in this research does not present any physical or psychological risks, risk of disadvantages, and does not intend any discomfort.

You should be aware that any criminal activity witnessed or uncovered during research must be reported to the responsible and appropriate authorities, even if this means overriding commitments to maintain your confidentiality and anonymity.

8. Benefits of this research project

While there are no immediate benefits from your participation, RESIST project will use the knowledge from the interviews to produce [*add here as relevant, e.g., climate change adaptation*].

9. Project Results

The results of the study will be disseminated for scientific purposes, in compliance with the ethical standards of the scientific community. It is guaranteed that the reports and scientific outcomes related to this project will not contain any identifying markers.

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You will be able to see the results of the study. These will be reported to the European Commission, in research articles and on repository platform for EC funded research. Raw data (audio recordings and transcripts) will not be made publicly available, only the analysis of data when it is possible to protect the privacy and anonymity of individuals. Some research results and news items will be posted on the project website: *[add when available]*

10. Questions and claims

If you have any questions about the research or if you would like to make a complaint on how you have been treated during your participation in this project, please contact the Principal Investigator (contact below), who will process it quickly and carefully. If you are unsatisfied with the way your complaint is being handled, you can also contact Dr Ildiko Ipolyi, the RESIST Ethics Manager ([email redacted]).

11. Organisation and Research Funding

RESIST has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101093968. *[add more if applicable]*

12. Ethical Review of the Project

The project has passed the ethics review process set by the European Commission *[enter info of any reviews that are required by your country or organisation]*.

13. Contact for more information

Principal Investigator

Name:

Email:

Phone:

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STATEMENT BY THE RESEARCHER/PERSON TAKING CONSENT

First, I have provided a copy of the research project information sheet or read it to the participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the participant understands the information provided about the content, purposes, and benefits of this project.

Second, I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the research and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent is informed, and has been given freely and voluntarily.

Name of Researcher _____

Signature of Researcher

Date (Day/month/year) _____

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PARTICIPANT STATEMENT

First, I confirm that I have been invited to participate in the RESIST project and that I consent voluntarily to be interviewed for the purposes of this study.

Second, I confirm that I have read (or been read to) the foregoing information, and I have been properly informed by [interviewer, add your name here] researcher in this project. I have received and understood the information provided about the content, purposes, and benefits of this project. I had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked were answered to my satisfaction. Therefore, I am aware that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. I understand that the recording and any transcript of the interview will be kept by [enter either "the interviewer" or the organisation, as applicable] only and destroyed [enter as applicable, for example 'two'] years after the end of the project, at the latest. I understand and agree that other authorised researchers may use my data in publications, reports, web pages, and other research outputs, on the condition that they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the information as requested in this form.

Name of Participant _____

Signature of Participant _____

Date (Day/month/year) _____

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